

INITIAL IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

Institutions: _____

Interviewee (Title and Name): _____

Interviewee Background

1. How long have you been:
_____ in your present position?
_____ at this institution?
_____ as a journalist?
2. What is your highest degree? _____
3. What is your field of study? _____

Social Identity and intersectionality

1. How do you identify yourself?
2. How do you describe your upbringing?
3. How do you describe your journalistic identity?
4. How is your gender identity influence your social and work life?
5. How do your other identities play out in your social and work life?
6. How do your identities intersect with each other?
7. Have you found difficulties in expressing your identity?
8. What factors hinder you from exercising your identity?
9. Where do you find yourself able to fully immerse yourself in your identity?
10. In what condition do you find yourself able to fully immerse yourself with your identity?
11. With whom do you find yourself able to fully immerse with your identity?
12. How do you think people perceived your identity?
13. What do you think of people with similar identity to you?

Journalistic Experiences and Identity

1. Why did you choose to be a journalist?
2. How do you stay motivated at work?
3. What are the roles of a journalist?
4. Do you find this job interesting or exhausting? Why?
5. Do you prefer to do this job for a long time? Why?
6. What is the most challenging experience in your journalistic experience? How did you handle it?
7. What is your greatest accomplishment as a journalist?
8. What kind of journalist are you?
9. What makes you unique as a journalist?
10. How do your identities influence your journalistic work?
11. Do your gender and other identities hinder you in leading the organization?
12. How do you think female journalists are different from a male journalist in doing the work?
13. How free are you to exercise your identities while doing journalistic work?
14. How do people perceive your identity while doing this job?
15. What is your definition of success as a journalist?
16. What are the qualities that a journalist should possess to be effective?
17. Describe your daily routine as a journalist

18. What skills do you employ when interviewing individuals for stories?
19. What kind of strategies and mindset are required for this role? Explain with example.
20. Describe a time you failed in this role and the lesson you learned
21. What is the biggest challenge that you foresee in this job?
22. How does newsroom diversity help the journalism industry?

Leadership Experiences

1. Briefly describe your role as it relates to the company's operation.
2. What kind of strategies and mindset are required for this role?
3. How would you describe your leadership style?
4. How do your identities influence your leadership style?
5. How would your colleagues describe your leadership style?
6. What kind of leader do people expect you to be?
7. Do your gender and other identities hinder you in leading the organization?
8. What are the main obstacles as a leader? And how did you overcome it?
9. What is your definition of success as a leader?
10. What are the unique qualities you bring to the table as a leader?
11. What strengths would you bring to this job?
12. How free are you in exercising your identities while leading the organization?
13. How do you monitor the performance of the people that you have to lead?
14. Are you able to delegate responsibilities efficiently?
15. What steps do you take to make sure that projects are completed on time, on budget, and to the proper standard?
16. What can you do to motivate a team?
17. What values are most important to you as a leader?
18. How do you handle disagreements with co-workers?
19. How do you respond to criticism?
20. Tell me about the hardest decision you've ever made as a leader. How did you decide which course of action was best?
21. Can you tell me about a time when you solved a problem for your employees/employer?
22. How do you measure your own performance at work?
23. What is the prevalent business strategy implemented in the company?
24. Is it working – why or why not?
25. What resources are available to support the business?
26. What is your greatest accomplishment as a leader?
27. Which supporting skills do you think are most important when it comes to leadership?
28. Are there any leaders that inspire you?
29. What do you think is most important in creating a positive culture?
30. How do you manage a diverse organization member?

Perceive Social Change

1. What changes would you seek to make as a leader in the organization?
2. What changes would you seek to make as a journalist in the journalism industry?
3. Why are changes necessary?
4. How would you motivate others to make changes?
5. What obstacles do you face in making changes?
6. What strengths would you bring to create changes?
7. How positive are you in bringing changes?
8. How far are you from your goals for a change?

9. What changes have you accomplished during your time as a leader?
10. How would newsroom diversity change the news organization?
11. How do your identities help create changes in the organization?

Innovation

1. Are you able to collaborate with others and accept new ideas?
2. How do you encourage your team to come up with creative and innovative ideas?
3. How do you define innovation in the journalism industry?
4. What kind of innovation does the journalism industry need today?
5. In your opinion, what's the greatest innovation in the journalism industry?
6. What kind of innovation have you accomplished during your time as a leader?
7. Tell me about a time when you took an innovative approach to solve a problem.
8. Tell me about a time when you thought of a better way to do something.
9. What is an innovation project that you have worked on in the past?
10. Through your innovation, what problems do you want to solve?
11. What are the most important skills needed for working innovation?
12. What are your biggest strengths and weaknesses regarding innovation?
13. What resources do you refer to when you need inspiration for new innovations?
14. What do you think about the role that innovation plays in business?
15. When do your best innovative ideas come to you?
16. What do you do to improve your and your team's creativity, innovation, and problem-solving skills?
17. How do your identities help you in bringing innovation in the workplace or journalism industry?
18. What are the challenges you find in bringing innovation to the organization?
19. How would newsroom diversity help the organization to innovate?
20. What are the factors to ensure the successful implementation of innovation?